
A Pragma-stylistic Analysis of Promising in Political Discourse

Noor Ali Qassim¹, Nawal Fadhil Abbas²

^{1,2}College of Education for Women, University of Baghdad, Iraq

Abstract: This study investigates the use of the promise speech act in political discourse from a pragma-stylistic perspective. To do so, the researchers examine two political speeches “President-elect Joe Biden’s victory speech” and “Justin Trudeau’s victory speech” and then made a comparison between them. The data are analyzed by using an eclectic model: a combination of Searl’s (1965, 1989) model and Sihite’s (2019) model. The study is descriptive and qualitative, since it does not deal with statistics and numbers. After applying the two models, the researchers found that both prime ministers use certain words to convey the act of promising such as the auxiliary “will” or by using the implied promise act which is used only by the American prime minister; he uses this style two times throughout the analyzed extracts. The researchers also found that both prime ministers use certain stylistic strategies to achieve their goals such as repetition which occurs twice in Trudeau’s speech, parallelism and fronting which appear twice in Biden’s speech. The research also shows that both prime ministers use active voice, and informal dialect, they do so to achieve their purposes.

Keywords: pragma-stylistic, political speeches, promise speech act, speech act theory

Introduction

Hickey (1993 as cited in Merza & Abbas, 2020, p, 333) was the one who originated the term “pragma-stylistics”, as a field of study in linguistics that refers to an important approach to text analysis. In other words, pragma-stylistics is concerned with how pragmatics contributes to the study of a text. Stylistics, on the other hand, and according to Hung (1969), is a subfield of linguistics. It is commonly known as the study of style. Pragmatics, on the other hand is defined as the study of language. Recently, pragmatics and statistics have been integrated to form a new approach of study known as pragma-stylistics, that is to say, it is an emergent approach used to study different types of discourse, written or spoken. Among such discourses, political discourse is chosen to be investigated in this study. Political speeches, as a subgenre of political discourse, are the means to consolidate the president's relationship with the people; this depends largely on the terminology used in the speech, as well as on the style of the speech. On election days, voters in democracies have the choice of casting a single ballot for one candidate or one party. Whether or not their choice is influenced by political convictions, it is almost certainly the result of verbal communication. According to Charteris-Black (2005), "In every type of political system, from the autocratic to the oligarchic to the democratic, leaders have relied on the spoken word to persuade others of the benefits that come from their leadership"(Charteris-Black 2005, p.1, as cited in Kulo, 2009).

Literature Review

2.1 Speech Act Theory

Austin first put up the Speech Act theory in 1962, and his students later published it. According to this view, speakers don't merely make assertions or refute others; occasionally, they create sentences utilizing particular verb types to communicate something other than what the sentence would normally mean. Performative verbs are any verbs that carry out a spoken act, for instance "promise," "warn," "bet," "dare," "fine," "resign," and "declare" (Fromkin et al, 2007, p. 206). Any speech act should be conducted in three acts simultaneously: a locutionary act, an illocutionary act, and a perlocutionary act, according to Leech (1983, p. 198). The act of speaking or writing a correct, meaningful sentence is known as a locutionary act. An illocutionary act is done when a sentence contains the speaker's or writer's intent to communicate something other than what is intended to be communicated. The perlocutionary act of the sentence is the result of this illocutionary act, which causes the speaker to act or respond in some way (Hussein, 2016). Moreover, speech acts can be defined in relation to speakers’ mutual beliefs, wants, intentions, evaluations and goals (Khalil & Abbas, 2018, p.263). According to Searle (1975) speech acts can be divided into five macro categories of illocutionary acts. These categories are:

Representatives: The point of this category is to bring the speaker to do something being the case. It represents the speaker's view of the world or how the speaker sees the world which can be reflected by his words which in turn reflect his thoughts, beliefs and ideologies. These thoughts and beliefs can vary between "swear", "suggest" and "hypothesize".

Directives: It is an attempt that is done by the speaker to persuade another person to do action. The speech acts in question are asking, commanding, giving commands, and proposing.

Commissives: They are statements that bind the speaker to a future course of action. Examples of this type include pledges, threat, offer, and promise.

Expressions: The words here convey an emotional condition. These speaking behaviors include expressing gratitude, remorse, welcome, and congrats.

Declaratives: They include words that by their uttering change the world. They typically need "an extra-linguistic institution". For instance, some declarations are related to language use "I define, abbreviate, name, call and dub".

2.2 Speech Act of Promising

To start with, the word "promise" is "originally derived from the Latin *pro*, which means forth, and *mittere* (to send) – referring to future" (Al-Saffar & Abbas, 2015, p.330). Promising as an illocutionary act is developed by Searle in 1965. He claims that a commitment is made according to five rules:

Propositional content rule: a promise must be based on the speaker's intention to perform the future act; neither a promise to have performed the act nor a promise that someone else will perform the act may be made (Searle, 1965).

Preparatory rules: If the promisee does not believe the promisee wants the action taken or even if the promisee secretly does not want the thing promised to be done, the promise is untrue; otherwise, the speaker will be giving a warning or threat, regardless of his or her intentions (Searle, 1965). In line with Searle (1965), the likelihood of a husband breaking his word to his wife that he won't be unfaithful during the following week is more likely to generate anxiety than relief. This is due to the fact that a speaker cannot commit to do something that he would always do.

Sincerity rule: The speaker must have the intended action in mind. Of course, someone can make a promise with absolutely no intention of keeping it, but in such a case, according to Searle, he is abusing the process (Searle, 1965).

The essential rule: It means saying something qualifies as taking on a commitment to do it (Searle, 1965).

2.3 Stylistics

Stylistics is a conceptual field that may work to create ideas that can be used to explain certain choices that individuals make while using language. Among other disciplines, pragmatic analysis, literary criticism, and discourse analysis can all make use of these concepts. The use of dialogue, dialects and idioms, active and passive voice usage, use of particular registers, sentence length distribution, and many other things are common stylistic characteristics. In addition to looking at what is happening outside of the language itself, stylistics also looks at the linguistic associations that the language's style reveals (Sihite, 2019). Stylistics is a branch of linguistics. It is frequently referred to as the study of style. Thinking in terms of style is nothing new. That goes all the way back to the rhetoric and poetry of antiquity. Its earliest form was the Roman word (*stilus*), which referred to a short reed stick used for writing on wax-coated boards (Hough, 1969, p.1). Since it began, styling has undergone a great deal of growth (Sihite, 2019). In his paper "Pragma-Stylistics Devices and Performative Study of Selected Oral Text" Sihite (2019) adopts an eclectic model that contains various elements, some of them deal with syntax and others with discourse. Among the elements introduced in his paper, the researchers of the present study select some that are appropriate to the data analysis. These elements include:

Connotation: Connotation is the broad range of associations, both "positive" and "negative" connotation that most words have by nature (Sihite, 2019).

Presupposition: The pragmatics branch of linguistics defines presupposition as an implicit assumption about the outside world or a background idea relevant to an assertion whose veracity is assumed during discussion. Presumptions include the following: A presupposition must be shared or assumed by the speaker and the addressee for a remark to be considered appropriate in the situation. The speech will typically continue to be a necessary assumption that may be linked to a specific lexical item or grammatical element in the utterance, whether it is delivered as an assertion, a denial, or an inquiry (Sihite, 2019).

Inference: An inference is defined as using logical deductions based on premises that are taken for granted. It is known as "a literary method utilized in the interpretation of literary text" (Sihite, 2019, p. 8).

Repetition: It means the use of the same word more than once in the same sentence (Abbas, 2020; Glatsh, 2021).

Syntactic deviation: Short (1969) states that there are many grammatical rules that control English sentences; therefore, there are a number of ways to write sentences by deviating from these rules. Leech (1969) suggests a way to differentiate between these types. It is by beginning with the link that is drawn between morphology and syntax.

Parallelism: It means bringing a word or phrase closer to the start of a sentence or clause than it would normally be, usually for emphasis (Nordquist, 2020).

Fronting: It means highlighting related ideas in a sentence by employing comparable words, clauses, phrases, sentence structure, or other grammatical aspects (Lynchburg, 2022).

2.4 Previous studies

The pragma-stylistic approach to the meaning of the linguistic acts Jonathan used in his Inaugural Speech as the democratically elected president of Nigeria in May 2011 was explored by Abuya in 2012. This study is based on Austin's and Searle's (1962) Speech Act theory (1969). According to the study, President Jonathan's Inaugural Speech tended to rely more on phrases conducted by commissive acts than by other speech acts. The study proved that politicians preferred to express their gratitude to the public following electoral victories.

Jennifer (2019) in her analysis of Zaynab Alkali's *Still Born* found that the most effective aspect of stylistics is the pragma-stylistics which concerns itself with the way in which an author uses language to enhance mental thoughts in the reader. She stated that this could be done by using pragmatic elements such as assumptions, presuppositions and inferences which could be interpreted by the reader via the language used in Zaynab Alkali's *Still Born*. Through her use of the theory of "Pragmatic Literary Stylistics", she concluded that pragmatic stylistics was a crucial instrument in the evaluation of a literary work. It was used to decipher the author's deliberate linguistic choices in order to reveal the text's meaning.

Al-Janaby and Al-Tememi (2021) did a study to investigate the pragma-stylistic aspects of illocutionary acts and the formal congratulatory letters in English and Arabic of politeness Strategies in some selected English and Arabic formal congratulatory letters written by English and Arabic officials. The findings of their study revealed that the highest frequency of speech acts used in the English data was that of assertiveness, while "expressive" occurred more in Arabic data. Besides, the FSA politeness strategy (Use appropriate forms of address) occurred equally in both English and Arabic data, but still appeared more in English. The use of (Exaggeration interesting and sympathy) came next in Arabic, while in English (Be optimistic) appeared more. Furthermore, as a result the use of exaggeration, (Hyperbole) was the most highly used stylistic device in Arabic. According to their study, Arabic officials frequently went overboard in glorifying those in positions of power, whereas English senior officials typically took a more restrained approach. Their results were useful in studies such as comparing different cultures and other related topics.

Based on these previous studies the researchers find that this topic has not been tackled before; therefore, the current study is intended to answer the following questions:

1. What are the linguistic triggers used by both prime ministers to convey the promise speech act?
2. What are the stylistic strategies used by both presidents?
3. What is the difference between American political speech and Canadian political speech?

Methodology

First of all, the present study is qualitative in nature for the fact that it does not use any statistics. Yet, in a qualitative analysis, researchers might need to show the results of their analysis by using tables and figures. In this case, they need to quantify the findings of the analysis depending on themselves. To answer the research questions and to achieve the purpose of the study, the researchers use an eclectic model that combines pragmatic and stylistic models. Searle's (1965) rules of performing the illocutionary act of promise and Searle's classification of speech acts (1975) are used. Besides, the researchers use a stylistic model following selected elements from Sihite (2019) and some other elements that the researchers find appropriate to the analysis. This study is following a set of procedures which are:

- 1- Reading the victory speeches many times in order to have a good and clear idea about them.
- 2- Identifying the utterances where the speech act is delivered.
- 3- Analyzing the extracts according to the eclectic model.
- 4- Comparing the speeches of both politicians.

Data analysis and Discussion

The researchers start by analyzing the two speeches from pragmatic and stylistic perspectives, then they move to discussing the result of the study and finally, they make a comparison between the styles of each prime minister.

Speech One

Justin Trudeau's victory speech: 'Our government is ready'

-*"That is exactly what we will continue to do"* (Macleans, 2021, para 3).

The speaker in this extract produces a "commissive" speech act by promising the people of Canada to work for them every single day. In fact, by saying this, the prime minister commits himself and his government to continue what the previous government has done. At the same time, the researchers cannot regard the speaker breaking one of Searle's (1965) rules of promising even when there appears to be one which is the "preparatory" rule. That is to say, the prime minister should not give a promise about things

that he already must do, however, he is doing so because of his situation; he has to comfort and satisfy people who voted for him to make them feel that they chose the right person.

The speaker uses the word “continue” which holds a positive connotation which indicates continuing what the previous government has done. The listener may “infer” that the government is more than willing to do everything. Simultaneously, the speaker can recognise that there is no political register for the prime minister’s speech, this is because the prime minister uses a simple style to give people a hint that he is just like them and wants to be close to them. The speaker uses the active voice instead of the passive to express his views and opinions in a way that is clear to everyone. He uses a short sentence to express his opinion. - *“Friends, I am ready to carry on with the work, my team is ready.”* (Maclean, 2021, para 6)

The prime minister uses “commissive” by uttering words that indicate future action by declaring “the government” and their readiness. Following Searle’s (1965) rules of promise speech act, the speaker does not break any one of these rules. The speaker should give people some promises about his future actions or plans to improve the nation’s situation to make them feel that what they gave did not go in vain.

The sentence holds a positive connotation; it gives a hint that the government is ready to take the responsibility; this is reflected in words like “ready, carry on”. Meanwhile, the speaker infers that the government attempts to keep its promise to give its citizens what their country deserves. The speaker uses an “active” voice to convey the message to the hearer in a simple and vivid way. Furthermore, the speaker uses the word “friends” which holds a connotation of closeness to make him more close to his people. The speaker uses repetition by repeating the word “ready” two times to emphasize the readiness, seriousness of his government. Again, there is no political register that appears in his speech which indicates that the speaker uses this style to give people a good impression about himself and his government. The speaker expresses his ideas and opinions by using a short length sentence. - *“We will stand up for you and work for you every single day”* (Maclean, 2021, para6).

The speaker produces a “commissive” act by promising people of Canada that his government will never stop. His government will do its best to reach people’s expectations. According to the rules, the speaker breaks the “preparatory” rule, since he promises about doing something that is expected from a government, at the same time the researchers find that the speaker is obliged to do so just to give people an insight about what the government will do.

The speaker infers that the government is on standby to serve and accomplish the citizens’ needs. The speaker repeats “for you” two times to emphasize that the government is caring about its citizens. He follows this by another emphasis by saying “every single day, instead of “every day” to emphasize their readiness. The sentence length is short. The speaker uses presupposition; by using the pronoun “we” he presupposes that the listener will infer what he means by “we” and “the government”.

- *“I will continue to be there for you. My friends from Papineau riding”* (Maclean, 2021, para 8).

The prime minister uses a “commissive” by uttering words that indicate a future action by declaring the government’s readiness and also by following the rule of “sincerity”. The sentence holds a positive “connotation”; it emphasizes the readiness of the speaker himself by saying “will, continue”. The speaker uses words that hold the same meaning as mentioned above; “continue on” is equivalent to “carry on”, in addition to the word “friends” which refers to the closeness between the speaker and people. Again, there is no register; the speaker uses simple terms instead of political ones in order to make the listener feel that the speaker is one of them, instead of thinking that he is one that has no feelings towards the public. The speaker uses an active voice to emphasize his closeness with others. He uses short sentences to express his views. From this sentence, the listener will infer that the speaker will never sit idle and help the people of Papineau.

Speechs Two

- *“I will work with all my heart to win the confidence of the whole people”* (The association Press, 2020, para 2).

The speaker produces a “commissive” speech act by uttering words that commit the speaker to do something in the future. The prime minister commits himself to work hard enough to win the confidence of people. Following Searle’s (1975) promise speech act rules, it seems for a while that the speaker breaks the promise rule of “preparatory”, due to the fact that he has the authority of doing everything, the speaker does not need to promise about things that he will already do. But it turns out that the speaker must do so because people want to know if they choose the right person or not.

The speaker uses a dialect that is similar to the hearer in order to make his speech clear, rather than using political terms “register” or talking with a style that regards above the listener comprehension. He applies the active voice for the same reason. The listener infers that the speaker will do his best to make people feel that he is trustworthy.

- *“For that is what America is about: The people. And that is what our administration will be about.”* (The association Press, 2020, para3)

Again, the speaker represents a “commissive” speech act by uttering words that contain future actions, “that is what America is about”, “what our administration will be”. The speaker explained to his voters how the government will be different from the previous one, “Trump’s government”. The speaker comforts American citizens that the government will be able to promote the nation’s condition.

The speaker uses a Question followed by a stimulus answer from the same person “the speaker” to emphasize the fact that the government is meant to serve the people of America. There is some rhyme in his speech by repeating “that is what”. At the same time, the speaker uses parallelism to have the same grammatical structure “that is what America... That is what our...” just to strengthen his speech and to get people’s attention. The listener will infer that the government is fully prepared to fulfill people’s needs.

-“ *It is the honor of my lifetime that so many millions of Americans have voted for this vision. And now the work of making this vision real is the task of our time*” (The association Press, 2020, Para 5).

The speaker produces an implied “commissive” speech act; he does not use words that indicate future action, rather the whole sentence functions as a commitment for future action. The speaker declares that his government is ready to make America rise again. However the speaker does so because he needs to gain people’s respect by appreciating those who vote for him.

The speaker uses fronting which is a kind of syntactic deviation. The sentence should be “The task of our time now is the work to make the vision real” in order to achieve people’s attention to emphasis on the idea of certainty which is making Americans rise again. The listener will infer that the speaker is about to do something great or good which is very different from what the previous government has done.

-“*To all those who volunteered, worked the polls in the middle of this pandemic, local election officials — you deserve a special thanks from this nation. To my campaign team, and all the volunteers, to all those who gave so much of themselves to make this moment possible, I owe you everything*” (The association Press, 2020, para 9)

The speaker represents an implied “commissive” act; he said “I owe you everything”, which is an implied indexation for a future action “promise”. There is no breaking for the rules that are involved in this quotation. The speaker shows that he appreciates teamwork and this makes the audience feel like he is not one that has no feelings about others. He appreciates every single effort that makes the moment of his election possible. The speaker does not break Searle’s promise speech act rules.

The speaker uses “parallelism”; he makes something that stands out from the whole sentence or paragraph such as “to all those who+verb”, the listener infers that the speaker is grateful to some specific people, those who “volunteer, worked during the pandemic...” The speaker uses a long length sentence to express his message.

The analysis shows that there are some similarities and differences between the two sides. According to the pragmatic aspect, the two prime ministers appear to follow Seale’s promise speech act by using the auxiliary verb “will” which occurs four times in the Canadian Prime Minister’s speech and two times in the American side. The study shows that the American Prime Minister uses an implied promise speaking act by using words like “owe”. The study finds that both prime ministers don’t break the promise speech act. Moving to similarity, the two prime ministers use active voice and talk with a dialect that is closer to the dialect of their public; therefore, their speech contains no political register. The difference between them is that the Canadian Prime Minister uses repetition by repeating the word “ready” two times and he doesn’t make a style-shift during his speech. On the other hand, the American Prime Minister uses some syntactic deviation techniques like parallelism two times and fronting one time only. They both use these techniques for making their citizens feel like they care about them and about the future of their country. The act of promising is an essential part of doing political speech. People need to hear the words that make them feel like they have chosen the right person to fulfill their needs. This depends on how the speaker who is responsible for this will formulate his speech in a way that makes people trust him.

Conclusions

The analysis of the two prime ministers in Canada and the US shows that they both follow Seale's promise speech act by using the auxiliary verb "will" four times in the Canadian Prime Minister's speech and two times in the American Prime Minister's speech. The American Prime Minister uses an implied promise speaking act by using words like "owe". Both prime ministers use the active voice and talk with a dialect that is closer to their public. The Canadian Prime Minister uses repetition by repeating the word "ready" two times and doesn't make a style-shift during his speech. The American Prime Minister uses some syntactic deviation techniques such as parallelism two times and fronting one time only. The act of promising is an essential part of doing a political speech, as people need to hear the words that make them feel like they have chosen the right person to fulfill their needs. Pragma-stylistics is a very important field for students and teachers are required to shed lights on this especially in political speeches as explored in the analysis.

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